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ENHANCING ENGLISH LEARNING WITH TECHNOLOGY: TIPS FOR TEACHERS.

Abstract: This thesis provides some tips for teachers on how to improve IT technology in English classes. As technology continues to advance and become an increasingly integral part of our lives, it is only natural that it has made its way into the classroom. From smartphones to tablets to laptops, students today have access to a variety of devices that can help them learn in new and exciting ways. One subject in which technology can be especially beneficial is English.

Keywords: Quizlet, Collaborative Learning, Adoptive Technology, Duolingo

INTRODUCTION

One of the most straightforward ways to incorporate technology into English classes is by using online resources to supplement learning. There are numerous websites and apps available that can help students improve their vocabulary, grammar, and writing skills. For example, 'Quizlet' is an excellent resource for creating flashcards and learning new vocabulary. 'Grammarly' is a popular app that provides real-time feedback on grammar and spelling mistakes. Teachers can make use of these resources by recommending them to students or incorporating them into classroom activities.

DISCUSSION

The way to improve IT technology in English classes is by incorporating multimedia into lessons. For instance, videos, images, and podcasts can be used as teaching aids to reinforce lessons and engage students. Teachers can curate content from platforms such as 'YouTube', 'Ted Talks', or 'Podcasts' to make lessons more interactive. For example, a teacher can show a clip from a movie to illustrate a certain point, such as a specific idiom or a cultural reference.

"Technology can also encourage collaborative learning, which is vital for the development of language skills. Teachers can use online tools such as 'Google Docs', 'Slack', or 'Trello' to facilitate collaboration on group projects or writing assignments. These tools provide a platform for students to work together and provide feedback to one another in real-time. Additionally, adding gamification to learning can make collaborative learning more engaging and fun", says John Keyler (professor of INHA university).

Lastly, teachers can improve IT technology in English classes by using adaptive technology to personalize learning. Adaptive technology is designed to provide a customized learning experience for each student based on their learning style and pace. For example, 'Duolingo' is a language learning app that uses gamification, artificial intelligence, and machine learning to personalize the learning experience based on each student's

performance. Teachers can use these tools to create personalized assessments or provide students with targeted practice activities.

Facilitate online language exchanges between your students and native English speakers from around the world. Websites like 'eTandem' and 'Conversation Exchange' connect language learners for virtual conversation practice. This provides an authentic and interactive experience while improving students' speaking and listening skills.

Integrate educational podcasts and videos into your lessons to expose students to authentic English content. Platforms like 'TED Talks', 'BBC Learning English', and 'ESLPod' offer a wealth of resources covering a wide range of topics. Assigning listening activities, discussions, and comprehension exercises based on these resources can enhance students' listening and comprehension skills.

Encourage students to use digital writing and grammar tools to enhance their written communication skills. Platforms such as 'Grammarly', 'Hemingway Editor', and 'Google Docs' can assist students in checking grammar, improving sentence structure, and obtaining real-time feedback on their writing. Utilizing these tools fosters independent learning and improves overall writing proficiency.

Games can also be used as a tool for English language learning. Games offer a fun and interactive way for students to practice their language skills. For example, 'Kahoot' is a game-based learning platform that allows teachers to create quizzes and surveys for their students.

The platform offers a wide range of topics, including language learning, and can be used to create engaging activities that challenge students to practice their vocabulary, grammar, and listening skills. Here you can find a guide on how to use 'Kahoot' in your lessons.

Promote online collaborative projects that allow students to work together on shared assignments or presentations. Platforms like 'Google Suite', 'Microsoft Teams', and 'Padlet' provide collaborative spaces where students can contribute, edit, and collaborate in real-time. These projects promote teamwork, critical thinking, and communication skills.

CONCLUSION

Integrating technology into English language classrooms opens up a world of possibilities for engaging and effective learning experiences. By using interactive language learning apps, online courses, immersive technologies, online exchanges, educational podcasts/videos, digital writing tools, and collaborative platforms, teachers can enhance students' English language skills and create an exciting learning environment. Embracing technology in English teaching not only expands the resources available but also prepares students to navigate the digital world they will encounter in their future endeavours.

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